

**Beyond Petipa and Before the Academy:
Plato, Socrates and Alexei Ratmansky's *Serenade After Plato's Symposium*¹**

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In 2016, having already risen to international prominence as a choreographer breathing new life into an art form that had seemed to many to be losing its relevance, Alexei Ratmansky choreographed a piece for American Ballet Theater (the company where he currently serves as Choreographer-in-Residence), *Serenade After Plato's Symposium*, set to Leonard Bernstein's 1954 composition of the same name for solo violin, strings and percussion. (For the sake of brevity, I will refer to this piece as *Serenade* from now on) The piece was hailed as a breakthrough by many critics, including Alastair Macaulay, at-the-time chief dance critic for the New York Times, who in his May 17 review describe it as "the most authoritatively original creation this bewilderingly versatile choreographer has given us." Among its many virtues, Macaulay singles out as the "true heart" of the piece its "dance evocation of the philosophical discourse of Socrates":

Ratmansky's ballet affectingly honors philosophical debate itself, showing us the supremely civilized kind of evening in which seven vividly different characters propose different ways of being, different forms of human energy. They coexist and support one another in intricate ways. . . . His same-sex partnering here is not erotically charged; yet affection and mutual supportiveness are wonderfully apparent. As a dance evocation of the philosophical discourse of Socrates — how amazing to encounter any dance in this terrain! — "Serenade After Plato's Symposium" may at once be ranked alongside Cunningham's "Septet" (whose subject, he wrote, was "Eros") and "Second Hand" (which was, John Cage once revealed, about the death of Socrates); and Mark Morris's "Socrates." (Macaulay 5/27/2016)

For better or worse, Ratmansky's work is largely responsible (along with the miraculous dancing of Herman Cornejo) for transforming me from a devoted-but-limited adult dance student into a

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full-on born-again balletomane, and I rarely find myself wanting to quarrel with anyone who praises his work for any reason. But this love has persisted *despite* not because of what registers for Macaulay as the dance evocation of philosophical discourse in this particular piece. “It **must** be said,” I find myself muttering, “Whatever its other virtues, the ‘supremely civilized’ and ‘deeply supportive’ evocation of ‘philosophical debate’ reflects the Socratic elenchus--that form of human intercourse at the heart of Plato’s dialogues--about as closely as most contemporary productions of *Sleeping Beauty* or *La Bayadère*, on Ratmansky’s view, reflect the spirit and style of the classics that are supposedly their sources.” And even before I have finished voicing this thought to myself, I have also, once again, started to object: “Why on earth *must* this be said? And to *whom*?” After all, as Marina Harss rightly underscores, Ratmansky’s piece is, first and foremost, a deeply musical response to Bernstein’s, and as Joan Acocella has pointed out, there are good reasons to think that the connection of Bernstein’s piece to the *Symposium* was little more than a pretentious after-thought.² So why think that anything of artistic significance rides on it if *Serenade*’s engagement with the relevant philosophy is neither very deep nor terribly accurate?

In the first part of this article, I argue that even if the particulars of the *Symposium* are for the most part of little importance for Ratmansky’s, its connection to platonic philosophy more generally is at the heart of its artistic power. The piece, I argue, is best understood as part of Mr. Ratmansky’s larger artistic project of “going back to go forward.”³ What it takes us back *to*, though, is less a particular platonic dialogue than it is to a neo-platonic vision of the harmony of

² Harss raised this point to me in conversation. Acocella’s can be found in Acocella 10/23/2016.

³ This quotation is taken from a lecture demonstration at The International Ballet Competition in Jackson, MS on June 21, 2018.

the universe out of which ballet as an art form is born. As such, what it gives us is at one and the same time both a powerful balletic and philosophical “vision scene.”

With a richer appreciation for what *Serenade* does offer, Part Two takes a careful look at those parts of the *Symposium* that *Serenade* declines most completely to register. The point is not that *Serenade* should have engaged more deeply with Plato’s dialogue (in addition to or instead of what it already does so powerfully). The point is rather that just those aspects of the *Symposium* with which ballet has yet to engage may be of special importance to it in the project of going back to go forward.

What is missing from *Serenade*, I argue, is Socrates himself, especially in so far as the figure of Socrates can be distinguished from that of Plato. While this Socrates is disclosed in the *Symposium* perhaps more vividly than anywhere else in the Platonic corpus, it for the most part the figure of *Plato*, whether mediated by the renaissance revival of Neoplatonism or Nietzsche’s critique of rationalism in *The Birth of Tragedy*, who has been the more consistent interlocutor in ballet. But if it is *Plato* who has presided at the birth and rebirth of ballet thus far, Ratmansky’s own work gives us good reason, I argue, to suspect that the figure who is more important for its future may be Socrates.

Part One: Beyond Petipa? Ratmansky, Plato and the Origins of Ballet

Aspects of *Serenade* make it difficult for the knowledgeable viewer to forego comparisons between the ballet and the dialogue from which it, following Bernstein’s piece, takes its name. Both dialogue and ballet have principle parts for seven men and one woman and it is often hard not to see traces of a specific character from the dialogue in the roles of particular dancers. Surely the stumbling of Danil Simkin is supposed to put us in mind of the drunken

Alicbiades. It is all but impossible to keep from seeing the “beauty” attributed to the speech of the poet Agathon in the meditative, introspective lyricism of Calvin Royal III. And surely the woman in the piece, a role created from Devon Teuscher, is meant to be the Priestess Diotima (who better to play a priestess than Teuscher). But such teases can seem to lead nowhere fast. The structure of the ballet refuses to track that of the narrative structure of the dialogue in any discernible way, and at crucial junctures the roles of individual dancers seem to be actually at odds with their most likely philosophical counterparts. This is perhaps most troublingly the case with respect to Teuscher’s role. As Julie Van Camp points out, this role includes an elegant pas de deux that is “full of traditional partnering”, which seems to fly in the face of the fact that anything recognizable as a romantic charge that circulates through the dialogue is one that passes among men. Describing the end of the piece, in which the seven men lean together, almost as if parts of one single body, toward a spotlighted Teuscher, Van Camp observes that “the men seem to yearn after her alone, not exactly in keeping with the dialogue . . . “ (Van Camp, 107). Not quite indeed.

Perhaps for reasons not too far removed from these, Robert Gottlieb, who considers the piece “the critical success of the decade” suggests that it would be even better “without the philosophical trimmings” (Gottlieb 10/27/2017). I respect Gottlieb’s judgment about anything ballet-related enough that it gives me pause to disagree with him. I am not convinced, though, that the “philosophy” at issue in this piece is best understood as a “trimming” that could be removed without significant artistic loss.

Mr. Ratmanksy’s ballet *about* conversation is, to my knowledge, his first (and only) explicit engagement with Plato. We should not be surprised, though, that when *conversation* becomes his subject, the occasion is a platonic one. Plato, if not Socrates himself, has been with

ballet from its inception. This might seem strange. Plato is famous for having Socrates propose to kick the epic and tragic poets out of his ideal republic. Such poets (Homer and Sophocles are his paradigm examples), Socrates argues, *deform* the souls of Athenian citizens by “nurturing and watering” lust, anger and other “desires, pleasures and pains.” The worry is that they encourage us to in effect put ourselves at the mercy of transient and conflicting appetites and desire instead of working to put them in their proper place, namely, by placing them within the context of a stabler whole of more enduring and harmonious ends. If Plato recognizes, though that (what we now call) the arts *can* function powerfully to stir up internal and external violence and conflict, they can also be a powerful means of healing it. When he turns his attention to dance, in the laws and elsewhere, that is the possibility that is at the forefront of his mind. Dance, he argues, is an important component of the education of the city’s guardians precisely because of what it contributes to the important work of organizing one’s own movements into a harmonious whole.

Ballet, Jennifer Homans argues, is in effect born out of a revival of interest in this platonic vision of harmony that led to establishment of the Académie de Poésie et de Musique in 1570. This academy was founded on the belief that “hidden beneath the shattered and chaotic surface of political life, lay a divine harmony and order—a web of rational and mathematical relations that demonstrated the natural laws of the universe and the mystical power of God” (Ibid, 5). In the spirit of their pedagogical predecessors, these academies, which aspired to the harmonious development of the whole person in body, mind and spirit and, included dance as a central part of its curriculum. As Homans puts it, the movements of the body, disciplined with poetic rhythm and meter and brought into accord with musical and mathematical principles, could tune him to celestial harmonies (Ibid, 6). Indeed, the connection between such harmonies

and dance was seen as so intimate that the Abbe Mersenne refers to God as “the great Ballet-Master” (Ibid, 6). One can see how powerful this animating inspiration continues to be within the art form in the body of work of a dancer like Herman Cornejo, whose every movement on stage seems to find, each time as if for the first time, the possibility that our own bodies might reflect, even help us re-attune ourselves to such harmonies.”⁴

Especially given Ratmansky’s passionate commitment to the artistic importance of ballet’s past for its present and future, it is perhaps fruitful to consider *Serenade* within the context of the most controversial aspect of his recent work: his labor-intensive, time-consuming and expensive efforts to reconstruct the traditional money-making ballet warhorses—*The Sleeping Beauty*, *La Bayadere* and *Swan Lake*—in a way that is faithful to the spirit, style, and the particular *steps* of the Petipa originals as accurately as possible. This is a move that has given pause even to some of his most consistent supporters, but Ratmansky has simply forged ahead. Perhaps what we have in *Serenade* is best understood as an extension of this trajectory. If *Serenade* pays only cursory attention to the specifics of the *Symposium*, it may well give us something else of great artistic value: an exploration of those early stages of ballet’s development *before* the interventions of Petipa, and even before those of Louis the XIV, which takes the form of a powerful recreation of the originary platonic vision that, as Homans puts it, “never really died” (8). So understood, the most important measure of the success of *Serenade* is the power with which it returns us to and explores that foundational hope that ballet might

⁴ One can see this aspect of Conejo’s dancing distilled and amplified in his solo in *Serenade After Plato’s Symposium*, which can be accessed here, starting at 2:07: <https://www.facebook.com/VailDance/videos/10156244386805935/UzpfSTE1ODE3ODcxODU3OjEwMTU2MjAxNDA4MjM2ODU4/?q=american%20ballet%20theater&epa=FILTERS&filters=eyJpbnRlcmFjdGVkX3Bvc3RzIjoie1wibmFtZVwiOlwiaW50ZXJhY3RlZF9wb3N0c1wiLFwiYXJnc1wiOlwiXCJ9In0%3D>.

contribute to whether and how we find our way from the “shattered and chaotic reality of political life” to a more enduring and harmonious order.

If we take the measure of *Serenade*'s success in this way, it can allow us to appreciate more fully what is most powerful about it. For one thing, it provides a context for appreciating just those aspects of the piece to which Mr. Macaulay draws most attention: the “highly civilized” and “deeply supportive” relationships between the seven male dancers in the piece. Whether the interactions between these dancers gives us an accurate picture, or *any* sort of picture of philosophical debate, it certainly gives us a powerful picture of the harmony that reigns in the ideal republic, and it even directs our attention to the source of the stability of that world: it's parts are organized in such a way that they support one another. And in true platonic fashion that harmony and stability is figured as powerfully at the intra-personal level as it is at the inter-personal level.

The intrapersonal personal level of harmony is bodied forth perhaps most powerfully in the solo *Ratmanky* created for ABT's Herman Cornejo. It is hard to imagine a dancer whose every movement on stage—no matter what role he is playing—is better suited to take us back, each time as if for the first time, to an appreciation for the potential of the human body to show us just what something deserving of the title “harmony of the spheres” might look like. As Acocella has put it, what is most remarkable about this extraordinary dancer,⁵ who can jump higher, move faster, and perform more revolutions of a turn than should be humanly possible, is not his virtuosity but his *clarity*:

Many young male dancers, particularly since Nureyev and Baryshnikov started the craze for male bravura, push the “show” steps as far as the possibly can; that is, until they are practically falling on the floor. Cornejo does not do this. He must certainly be pushing—he gets so far—but he never, ever sacrifices form. . . . This is true even when he is in the

⁵ At age sixteen, Cornejo became the youngest person ever to win the esteemed Moscow Ballet Competition.

air, the hardest place to hold a shape, because gravity is working against you. You, but not him. (Acocella 11/08/2004)

In *Serenade*, Ratmansky creates a solo for Cornejo that isolates, amplifies and celebrates just this aspect of his dancing.⁶ Even as he is moving through a series of shapes with extraordinary speed, he somehow also seems to linger over each one, showing it to us not only as an interesting *part* of what is going on but also and at the same as a complete, internally perfect, end in itself.

What Ratmansky achieves in Cornejo's solo happens six more times in *Serenade*.

Something Ratmansky is especially known for is his ability to see in a particular dancer those movement possibilities that are most distinctly *theirs* and to create roles for them that zero in on just those possibilities and afford the dancer an opportunity to take them as far as they are able.

As both Macaulay and Acocella acknowledge, *Serenade* takes this Ratmansky signature to a whole new level. Macaulay articulates this point by saying that ballet shows us seven “vividly different . . . ways of being, different forms of human energy,” while Acocella sums up the observable *result* of what she has just described as an intense and often painful rehearsal process by observing that the dancers look like they “think somebody loves them” (Macaulay 5/17/2016; Acocella 10/23/2016). Acocella formulates her point so simply that it would be easy to miss its depth and significance. For our purposes what is most important is that by drawing attention to the particular kind of *love* between choreographer and dancer upon which the artistic power of *Serenade* depends, Acocella points us toward what is perhaps the deepest and most important point of contact between that piece and the particular dialogue from which it borrows its title. For what she makes it easier to see is that this particular kind of love is a species of that form

⁶ The solo can be viewed here:

<https://www.facebook.com/VailDance/videos/10156244386805935/UzpfSTE1ODE3ODcxODU3OjEwMTU2MjAxNDA4MjM2ODU4/?q=american%20ballet%20theater&epa=FILTERS&filters=eyJpbnRlcmFjdGVkX3Bvc3RzIjoieIwibmFtZVwiOlwiaW50ZXJhY3RlZF9wb3N0c1wiLFwiYXJnc1wiOlwiXCJ9In0%3D>.

which lies at the heart of the *Symposium itself*. Socrates introduces the relevant form of love in his speech and attributes his understanding of it to the Priestess Diotima who, he claims, initiated him into its mysteries. He describes it as a form of conversation that can be illuminated through comparison with (sexual) intercourse:

Some people are pregnant in body, and for this reason turn more to women and pursue love in that way, providing themselves through childbirth with immortality and remembrance and happiness, as they think, for all time to come; while others are pregnant in soul . . . and these are pregnant with what is fitting for a soul to bear and bring to birth. And what is fitting? Wisdom and the rest of virtue.
(Symposium, 56)

When such a person “makes contact with someone beautiful and keeps company with him, he conceives and gives birth to what he has been carrying inside himself all along” (Ibid, 57). Together with the person who has inspired him—who has drawn out what was inside—he “nurtures” these “newborn” ideas. This, according to Socrates, creates a bond that is stronger than that shared by biological parents because the ideas that they raised together are “more beautiful and more immortal.”⁷

We do not have to follow Socrates in his assessment of the relative value of newborn babies and newborn ideas to see some of the point in the comparison he draws. Nor is it hard to see how this comparison might be extended to include the intercourse that would help to nurture and actualize the movement potential that an individual dancer carries. Insofar as *Serenade* just is some specific movement possibilities carried to term, it is an instantiation of the love that *The Symposium* is about. Insofar as they are carried to term, those possibilities take the form of seven ways of being that are, as Macaulay observes, both “vividly different” integrated with and

⁷Ibid., 57. The transformed relationship that is constituted by philosophical conversation is not just *described* in the *Symposium*. It is demonstrated in the intercourse between Socrates and Agathon. On hearing Agathon’s “beautiful” speech, Socrates “teems with ideas and arguments about virtue” and “gives birth” to the memory of his encounter with Diotima that he has been carrying inside him.

supportive of one another, they show us a truly utopian vision of the platonic ideal. For as Ratmansky shows it to us, the harmonious order of the ideal republic is at least consistent with, maybe even the condition for the possibility of, the flourishing of individuals *as individuals* rather than requiring the sacrifice of it, as many students of both the *Republic* and of the demanding artform of ballet are perhaps right to fear.

As I have described it, *Serenade* offers us a vision of an ideal that is, at one and the same time, philosophical and balletic. Part of what is so compelling about the piece is it shows how deeply intertwined those two visions—at least at one time—were. And it raises a question about how deeply intertwined they still are, or (ideally) should be. At the same time, it suggests that if we want to help us to understand the *structure* of *Serenade*, we are better off looking to the structure of traditional ballet than to the narrative structure of the *Symposium*. As Peter Scholl describes it, the “ballet blanc” or “vision” scene is one standard part of the “template for late nineteenth-century ballet” which includes “narrative sequence culminating in a mad scene, vision scene, resolution, divertissement” (Scholl, 24). One paradigmatic example is Prince Desiré’s “vision” of Aurora in Act Two of *The Sleeping Beauty*.⁸ In order to motivate Prince Desiré to hack his way through one-hundred years of underbrush, find Aurora, and wake her up, The Lilac Fairy shows him a vision of Aurora that leads him to fall in love with the beautiful princess. There are important precedents for a “vision scene” that stands on its own instead of forming a part of the dramatic structure of a three-act ballet. As Scholl points out, this is how Stravinsky and Balanchine understood the first ballet that they created together, *Apollon Musagète*. I will return to this collaboration in Part Two, but for now, the point is merely this. Like the Lilac

⁸ This video compares Ratmanksy’s recent reconstruction of this scene for ABT and La Scala with Sergei Vikharev’s reconstruction of it for the Marinsky Ballet:
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NxMfVNQQNk8>.

Fairy, Ratmansky offers us a beautiful vision and perhaps, as is the case with Prince Desiré, the key question is: will we fall in love with it, and if so, what might that motivate us to do?

If we think of *Serenade* as offering us such a “vision scene”, it can, at the same time return us to and illuminate even that part of the *piece* that fits least well into that vision: namely the role created for Devon Teuscher. Especially for those who are inclined (sometimes perhaps with good reason) to criticize Ratmansky’s work for continuing to perpetuate just those cis white male stereotypes that persist as a problem within ballet, Teuscher’s role is likely to register as the most problematic aspect of the piece.⁹ In the *Symposium* itself, only Diotima’s ideas are present. Why convert her role into one that is full, as Van Camp puts it, of traditional partnering and makes *her* the focus of erotic longing while at the same time soft-peddling the distinctly homoerotic forms of longing that circulate so explosively in the dialogue itself? Even if one is considering the role, as Harss does, strictly from the point of view of musical and choreographic structure, there are reasons to be dissatisfied:

The pas de deux between Gomes and Devon Teuscher, who shows up midway through the ballet, is something of a puzzle. Who is this woman? Why is she there? She seems to represent something apart from the others, not a human relationship but a figure of fate—the tragic dimension of love. I’m still not convinced by the end of the ballet, though [Harss is, I take it, referencing the final tableau in which all the men seem, as Van Camp puts it, to be yearning for this mystery woman]: It seems too rushed, too busy, too abrupt. Though it matches Bernstein’s mad dash to the finish, it doesn’t quite wrap things up. (Harss 10/20/2016)

Harss, I would argue, zeros in on just those questions that need to be raised about Teuscher’s role: Who is she? Why is she there? How are we to understand her lack of integration with the male utopia that she seems to interrupt? How are we to understand the puzzling final tableau in which all the men, still joined together in a complicated web of mutual support that allows them

⁹ Footnote here that references the sources of such criticism and acknowledge that I am not going to consider them: Odessa review, problem article, Dance and Stuff podcast, facebook exchange.

to reach, as if one single integrated body, longingly toward Teuscher in a spotlight? And I would not dispute her sense that, whatever is going on, it doesn't quite work. I do, though, want to suggest one way of understanding what is perhaps being attempted, even if it is only achieved.

If what we see in *Serenade* is less an engagement with the specifics of the *Symposium* than it is with the neo-platonic origins of ballet, the thought that Teuscher is “obviously Diotima,” As Van Camp puts it, starts to seem less compelling, even though the very fact that the ballet, like the dialogue, has roles for seven men and one woman seems to invite us to do just that. If, though, what we are seeing is an exploration of the early stages of ballet's development, then the very aspects of her role to which Harss draws attention—the abruptness of her appearance, her lack of integration with the male dancers who, until her appearance, have been so seamlessly and harmoniously related to each other—start to look like the *point* rather than a *problem*. Perhaps the only thing in this piece *about* harmonious relations—this piece *about* the enduring power of the ideal of harmony, for better and for worse, in ballet as an art form—that cannot be made to fit together harmoniously are the stages of the development of ballet itself. In other words, perhaps part of what this piece is thinking about--and seeking to draw to our attention with the abrupt and disruptive appearance of Teuscher—is the transition from the earliest of stages of ballet, where the dominant visual metaphor for harmony is just the kind of all-male utopia it has so powerfully *shown* (and attention is correspondingly on *male* dancers) to a stage in which the dominant visual metaphor for such harmony shifts instead to the pas de deux (and the spotlight shifts from the male virtuoso to the ballerina). So understood, it would be unclear, and important that it *remain* unclear why, or even who, the reconstituted all-male community is reaching toward in the final tableau: are they reaching *back* toward Diotima? Forward toward Aurora? Perhaps both at the same time? If ballet must go back in order to go

forward, perhaps what it has to go back to is the question of how these stages of its own development do or do not fit together—how *unseemless* the transitions between one stage and another are? The question is more an artistic than an historical one: what sense can *ballet* make of these different parts of its own past as it explores different ways of gathering them into itself in order to move toward its future? The achievement of *Serenade*, as I understand it, is that it puts us in a better position to *ask* this question, and to understand its significance, even if it is not yet *answering* it.

II. **Beyond *Serenade*: Ratmansky, Socrates and the future of ballet**

As I have interpreted it, one could not remove the “philosophical trimmings” from *Serenade* without at the same time destroying its artistic power. In fact, part of what is so powerful about it as a work of art is how deeply intertwined it shows philosophical and artistic power can be. At the same time, if one looks to *Serenade* for some sort of sustained engagement with the particular philosophical text from which it borrows its title, one will miss even most of what is *philosophically* powerful about it. It would be *perverse* to ask this ballet, which if anything is, as Harss suggests already perhaps trying to do *too much*, to do even more, or to exchange something which it does so powerfully for something that it does not do. Even so, there are, I will try to convince you, good reasons to pay careful attention to what ballet may have to gain from paying a deeper kind of attention to the *Symposium* itself.

In a certain sense, this particular dialogue has already *been* an especially important one for ballet, although whatever engagement there has thus far been has, for the most part, been indirect, a function of ballet’s engagement with another philosophical interlocutor, Friedrich Nietzsche. As a college student, he wrote a detailed and enthusiastic essay about it, at graduation

he declared it to be his “lieblingslied” (that is, his favorite book) and he references it in “The Attempt at Self-Criticism,” which is written in response to that work of his that has been most important for ballet, *The Birth of Tragedy Out of the Spirit of Music*.¹⁰

The part of the *Symposium* that interested Nietzsche most as a college student, as well as the part that it is perhaps easiest to see reflected in *The Birth of Tragedy*, is the Speech of Alcibiades.¹¹ If ballet is dealing with its discontinuities and interruptions in *Serenade*, Philosophy is dealing with its own in the *Symposium*. The events it dramatizes take place at the house of Agathon, a tragic poet who has taken first prize at The Festival of Dionysus. Agathon invites everyone over so that they can continue to celebrate. Everyone is still hung over from the previous night’s debauches, though, and when Socrates arrives, uninvited but not unwelcomed, they decided to put away the wine, send away the dancing girls and indulge in further competition instead of further drinking. The competition they settle on is a variation on the competition that Agathon has just won: a competition not for the best dramatic tribute to Dionysus but instead for the best speech in praise of a god so often neglected that he does not even have a proper name: the god of love. Everything goes according to (the altered) plan, with each of the guests, including Socrates, giving his speech in turn. Then Alcibiades shows up and does his level best to disrupt whatever order there has been to the evening’s proceedings.

Alcibiades is the beautiful, charismatic, testosterone-exuding, military hero upon whom the hopes of Athens (at the time when Agathon’s party supposedly takes place) confidently rest. Like Socrates, he is a late arrival and when he gets to the gathering, he doesn’t just interrupt it, he changes its terms yet again. He refuses to play by the rules that the other participants have

¹⁰ Blue (2016), 2 & [get pg. # and reference for “Attempt at Self-Criticism.”]

¹¹ The title of his college essay about the dialogue is titled, “On the Relationship of Alcibiades’ Speech to the Rest of the Speeches in Plato’s *Symposium*” (cf. Blue).

agreed upon, refusing to give a speech in praise of the god of love and insisting instead upon making *Socrates* the subject of his speech.

As Jacob Howland has pointed out, Alcibiades speech is “the longest direct discussion of Socrates’ nature in the Platonic corpus” (Howland, 29). An important part of what it does is zero in on “various dimensions of Socrates’ *atopia* or “strangeness” . . . that mark him as one who is “out of place” or even “without place” (atopos) (ibid, 29). To take only the two most obvious examples, Socrates refuses to be placed into the role of “teacher,” despite the powerful and wealthy citizens, including Alcibiades and Plato himself who claim to be his students, and he refuses to abide the thought that there is some special *place* for philosophy: it happens whenever or wherever there is an outbreak of the kind of soul transforming conversation into which Diotima initiated him.

Something else that Alcibiades makes clear in his speech is just how difficult, disorienting and even terrifying that form of transformation can be; it turns a person into a *stranger to himself*. In his speech Alcibiades recounts in vivid, steamy detail his frustrated efforts to seduce Socrates into entering with him into a familiar and accepted form of love relationship between men, one in which a younger man whose soul is still in the process of forming takes a mature male lover who in return takes on responsibility for his moral education.¹² What distresses him is that Socrates neither accedes nor breaks off relations with Alcibiades but instead involves him in the kind love relationship that he has described in his speech. When, as a result, Alcibiades finds himself teaming with new and disruptive ideas, it leaves him terrified and confused:

Well, something much more painful than a snake has bitten me in my most sensitive part—I mean my heart, or my soul, or whatever you want to call it,

¹² This traditional form of love relationship is one of the main foci of Pausanias’s speech.

which has been struck and bitten by philosophy, whose grip on young and eager souls is much more vicious than a viper's and makes them do the most amazing things. (Ibid, 59)

He recognizes the responsibility that these new-born ideas place on him to transform his life—"my very own soul started protesting that my life—*my* life—was no better than the most miserable slaves"—but he balks at the difficulty of changing in the necessary ways and runs away instead. (ibid, 66-7). This leaves him in a state of permanent war with himself that has started to spill out in various ways into the world around him.

These aspects of Socrates "nature" and of the philosophical conversation that he practices (how difficult, disruptive and frightening it is) find in *Serenade* "no surface that consent[s] to reflect it."¹³ It is for this reason that my gut rebels again Macaulay's description of the "deeply civilized" and "mutually supportive" harmony that we see in the male dancers as an "evocation of the philosophical discourse of Socrates." It may be many artistically and philosophically significant things, but it is *not* that.

A piece that arguably *does* engage, to *some* extent, with these excluded dimensions of the *Symposium*, albeit obliquely Balanchine and Stravinsky's first collaboration, *Apollon Musagète*, which was first performed in 1928. What engagement there is with the *Symposium* in this famous piece is mediated through engagement with *The Birth of Tragedy*. If anything in the young Nietzsche's *lieblingslieder* remains important for his controversial early published writings, it is surely the explosive drunken eruption of Alcibiades in its latter half. If one goes to the *Symposium* with Nietzsche in mind, it is difficult *not* to see in Alcibiades' mocking, tortured,

¹³ I borrow these words from Henry James. They occur in his description of an aestheticizing tendency that, I take it, he recognized a constant danger internal to his own novel-writing practice. Here is the full quotation: "It was a conspiracy of silence, as the *cliché* went, to which no one had made an exception, the great smudge of mortality across the picture, the shadow of pain and horror, finding in no quarter a surface of spirit or speech that consented to reflect it" (James, 347).

ambivalent and overtly sexual provocation of Socrates a kind of ur text for the clash between the “Apollinian” and the “Dionysian” around which *The Birth of Tragedy* revolves.

If Socrates and Plato have been with ballet from its beginnings, for much of its life its relationship to them has been mediated by *The Birth of Tragedy* which both tells a “story”¹⁴ about the birth of Greek Tragedy--out of the conflict between two fundamental artistic principles, the “Apollinian” and the “Dionysian”—and its death, which is brought about when the “Apollinian” principle is succeeded by an “altogether new born daemon called Socrates” (Nietzsche, 60). When the Apollinian has degenerated into the “socratic,” a once productive conflict between an appreciation for order and a desire for freedom hardens into a “rigid,” “menacing” and “repressive” military encampment (Ibid, 27-8). In this story, the utopian possibility of a “rebirth” of tragedy is imagined as the possibility that man [sic] might “forget how to walk and speak” and once again “fly into the air dancing.” It is not therefore hard to see how this story might have fired the imagination of dancers as powerfully as it has sometimes alienated those most verbal of Peripatetics, academic philosophers.¹⁵

Nietzsche’s influence on the history of *modern* dance is widely recognized. One does not have to be an insider to know of Nietzsche’s importance for greats of modern dance such as Isadora Duncan, who purportedly kept her copy of *The Birth of Tragedy* by her bedside and read it (in her own words “religiously”) and Martha Graham. His importance for the dialectical

¹⁴ Issues that arise about the status of this “story”: historically accurate narrative? Origin story? Myth?

¹⁵ While Nietzsche’s *The Birth of Tragedy out of the Spirit of Music* all but destroyed his academic career and is considered by even many of his biggest philosophical advocates an embarrassing youthful indiscretion at best. The distaste for the book with contemporary analytic aesthetics is reflected in the table of contents of the in many ways excellent *Aesthetics: A Comprehensive Anthology* by Steven M. Cahn and Aaron Meskin. The book offers two tables of contents, the first organized chronologically and the second, according to “issues in philosophical aesthetics.” Although an excerpt from *The Birth of Tragedy* is included in the volume, it is the only entry from the volume that does not show up at all in the “alternative table of contents.” In other words, it appears that Nietzsche, although of a certain history interest has nothing to contribute to any of the central issues in philosophical aesthetics.

development of ballet, although perhaps less widely recognized, is arguably no less profound. In the first historical study to place modernist ballet fully in the context of contemporaneous developments in the broader cultural context of Russian arts and letters, Tim Scholl argues that Nietzsche, whose influence extended to “virtually all areas of Russian turn-of-the-century art and culture” and could be felt as early as 1890, the year that *The Sleeping Beauty*, the most commercially successful collaboration between Marius Petipa and Pyotr Tchaikovsky and arguably one of the most important ballets for the development of the art form. That influence comes to the surface in its most sustained and explicit way, though, in what Scholl convincingly argues is in effect a dialogue between three legendary works—Nijinsky’s *Afternoon of a Faune* and *The Rite of Spring* on one hand and *Apollon Musagète* on the other.

Nijinsky’s *Rite*, Scholl argues, represented the “logical end” to a Dionysian challenge to ballet as the “Apollonian beauty of the ‘classical’ ballet” from within. That challenge had taken shape in earlier forms in the work of choreographers like Fokine who, following Duncan, not only turned to Greek themes for their ballets, but also began to question the “rigors” and the ballet’s “dans d’école,” and to explore the possibility of producing dances without the “attendant companies, schools and bureaucracies” (Scholl, 53). Nijinsky took things even further, not only by scandalously depicting explicit acts of masturbation, but by thoroughly rejecting both classical technique (substituting in its place a vocabulary that was “weighted and coarse, contracted and unlovely”) and the kind of stage space (the proscenium stage) that it had evolved to fill. He choreographed his pieces instead for a shallow, foreshortened stage which literally left no room for the expansive, virtuosic displays upon which traditional ballets depended (70-1,78.). As Nikolai Minsky put it in his review of *Faune*, “Apollo cedes place to Dionysus, and the curtain falls” (71).

The Apollinian response to this apotheosis of Dionysus takes its most visible form in *Apollon Musagète*. In his autobiographical writings, Stravinsky acknowledges his explicit conception of this piece as a reassertion of the Apollinian principle:

In classical dancing, I see the triumph of studied conception over vagueness, of the rule over the arbitrary, of order over the haphazard. I am thus brought face to face with the eternal conflict in art between the Apollonian and Dionysian principles. The latter assumes ecstasy to be the final goal—that is to say, the losing of oneself—whereas art demands above all the full consciousness of the artist. There can, therefore, be no doubt as to my choice between the two. And if I appreciate so highly the value of classical ballet, it is not simply a matter of taste on my part, but because I see exactly in it the perfect expression of the Apollonian principle. (Scholl, 94)

Apollon Musagète begins, Scholl argues, exactly where Nijinsky's *Faune* so scandalously leaves off: with a “wild, half human” youth pleasuring himself, this time by strumming a lyre that rests suggestively on his lower hips. It then unfolds before us the transformation of this youth into the God Apollo by means of his gradual mastery of the full-range of the classical movement vocabulary but also through the gradual transformation of the static, flattened use of stage space that had been central to Nijinsky's deep and thorough challenge to grand ballet traditions.

Not only did Balanchine and Stravinsky explicitly conceive of *Apollon Musagète* in Nietzschean terms, they also conceived as just the kind of self-standing “white ballet” or “vision scene” that I have argued we may have in *Serenade*. Stravinsky especially, Scholl demonstrates, was interested in the idea of a self-standing white ballet that relieved it of its narrative function within a larger whole and returned it to its origins in a “divertissement that had promulgated pure, or abstract dance” as the Apollinian dance par excellence and understood *Apollon Musagète* to be such a decontextualized vision scene. *Apollon Musagète* certainly does not give us a ballet purged of narrative. What it does arguably afford, though, is another extraordinarily powerful vision of an originary impulse out of which ballet is, in *Apollon Musagète* itself, reborn.

What is most important for the present purpose about this second, extraordinarily powerful “vision scene” is how thoroughly *platonian* this vision of the “reassertion of the Apollinian” is. This is especially evident if we pay attention to the broader cultural context within which Scholl places that reassertion and which had its center of gravity in the Russian journal, *Apollon*, published in St. Petersburg from 1909 to 1917, for which Nietzsche also served as an important touchstone.¹⁶ This periodical, which included articles on music, theater, dance, poetry, architecture and painting, and published historical and theoretical essays alongside reviews, reflected a renewed commitment to the artistic importance of “academics” that went beyond the dance academy and extended to sustained historical and theoretical study of the arts. In other words, the rebirth of ballet in the collaboration of Balanchine and Stravinsky depended upon *both* the academies that locate their own origins in Plato: both the *dans d’école* and western academic institutions.

Balanchine wore this extraordinary erudition lightly. As Solomon Volkov recounts, when he approached Balanchine about the project that became *Balanchine’s Tchaikovsky*, he pitched it as “a children’s book about Tchaikovsky—something simple and unpretentious” because he was “well aware of [Balanchine’s] dislike of elaborate, ‘meaningful’ statements, of pompous eloquence” (Volkov, 17-8). In Episode 50 of the podcast *Conversations on Dance*, Edward Villella (Balanchine principle dancer as well as founder and former artistic director of Miami City Ballet) underscores how deeply important that unspoken and often unrecognized erudition was for the pieces that Balanchine created. Speaking of his work with Balanchine on *Prodigal Son* Villella recalls,

He always had a style, whatever it was, a style in each of these ballets, and he would create a world for you, and you had to understand all of that, what was that world. I

¹⁶ cf. Scholl, 81.

looked at the set, I looked at the fence, then I watched the fence become a table, I watched the fence become a crucifixion, I watched the fence become a boat, and I watched the fence go back to being a fence. So, uh, as I was looking at all of that, I had heard of something called Russian constructivism, but it wasn't a style that I knew very much about, so I started to think and by God, that ballet is based on Russian constructivism, and so these things were starting to show themselves. So again, I was just acquiring knowledge, on how to operate, how to make a character, how to make a role, not an easy thing to do if you don't have a long background to all of that stuff and the director and choreographer hadn't given you many hints. . . I didn't see him again until maybe the third performance, and he came back stage afterwards and he told me I was having difficulty getting into the pas de deux . . . and I can't get what he's trying to show me, I just can't get it. And he got exasperated with me and he said, "Byzantine Icons, dear, Bysantine Icons, . . . And I thought, "Byzantine icons? What is this?" and I went and I got every book I could possibly find on Byzantine icons. There was the entire pas de deux of *Prodigal Son*. So that in itself informed me that I had to be looking for all of those things in all of the other ballets. (minutes 9:20—12:50)

Part of what Villella's remarks illuminate is how the deep and ongoing context for Ratmansky's own turn to the archival resources of Harvard University.¹⁷

My reason for emphasizing the deeply *platonic* resonance in ballet's "reassertion of the Apollinian" is to draw attention to how limited is the engagement of this second "vision scene" (extraordinarily powerful though it is in other respects) with those parts of the *Symposium* that *Serenade* declines to register at all. What it registers is merely the *conflict* between Alcibiades and Socrates that it depicts. It does not register as artistically significant the vividly specific Socrates that the speech discloses nor anything of the nature of the first-person experience of the Socratic elenchus that it affords.

¹⁷ Villella's remarks also help to illuminate just how deeply the recent revitalization of ballet, to which Miami City Ballet has contributed so significantly, depends upon cultivating not just technical virtuosity but also a wide-ranging intelligence that is the condition for the possibility of dancers taking shared artistic responsibility for the artistic life of the works that they perform. One can see the fruits of that commitment not just in the extraordinary quality of the company's dancing, which took the international ballet community by storm, but also the *Conversations on Dance* podcast, which was created and is hosted by two former core dancers from the company (Rebecca King Ferarro and Michael Breedon). This podcast, no less than *Apollon*, brings together personal and professional narratives with lengthy and detailed scholarly discussions of ballet history and criticism and is punctuated throughout by attention to the open question about the conditions for the possibility of wholistic well-being for the art form as well as the many individuals who give their lives in various ways to it.

A powerful dramatic depiction of exactly what is missing can be seen in *The Public Theater's* recent production of Tim Blake Nelson's new play, *Socrates*.¹⁸ This play, which integrates material from multiple dialogues in order to build its dramatic portrait, introduces us to the title character through the eyes of those who perhaps love him the most: his two most famous, most devoted and, arguably, most frustrated "students," Plato and Alcibiades.¹⁹ The play opens when a resistant young student is brought to Plato's academy and placed under his tutelage. When this unidentified student angrily confronts Plato failing to prevent Socrates' death, a grieving but unapologetic Plato gives him a front row seat (his own) at a series of events that he both witnessed and participated in and is still seeking to understand. Once this unnamed student²⁰ takes his place as a witness, the first thing he sees is Alcibiades' speech before Socrates and the other guests at Agathon's party. This scene follows the text of the speech so closely that it might be fair to describe it as "spoken word" (with the caveat that of course it is spoken in English and so, in fact contains *none* of the words of the dialogue in its original form).²¹

This production keeps front and center the struggle between Alcibiades and Socrates—and in so doing, the contest between those forms of love embodied in a traditional pederastic relationship and Socratic conversation respectively. At the same time, it also dramatizes an

¹⁸ My discussion of this production is based on two viewings of it, first on 4/27/2019 and then again on 6/01/2019. *The Public* declined to my request to see a copy of the as-yet unpublished script, either for the purposes of this article or for the benefit of my students in Starkville, Mississippi. If they had any advice, which I also solicited, about other ways a copy might be obtained, they elected to keep it to themselves. I found this an odd way to act on their stated mission of contributing to the artistic education of the public.

¹⁹ I include scare quotes around "student" here because as the play underscores, despite the many who are eager to claim him, are necessary because despite the many, including Plato and Alcibiades, Socrates persistently denies being a "teacher."

²⁰ The final lines of the play resolve any doubt that may have lingered that we are supposed to identify this student with Aristotle.

²¹ It may in fact be a "spoken word" reproduction of one translation or another but without access to a script it is not possible to know.

ongoing struggle between *Plato* and *Socrates* and, so, between Socratic forms of conversation and those that Plato fosters within what becomes his academy. Throughout the ensuing drama, he returns repeatedly not just to the question of what and why Socrates and the people of Athens did what they did, and what it all meant, but also to the question of whether Plato has betrayed his mentor—whether Socrates and the elenchus that he devoted his life to have been lost in Plato’s translation of them both into writing and into the academy. The play repeatedly returns us to that question by emphasizing *differences* between the relationship that Plato cultivates with Aristotle and that which Socrates cultivates with his interlocutors, differences that the play marks most obviously by showing Plato to insist upon his role as Aristotle’s “teacher” (even in the face of Aristotle’s ambivalence) while Socrates repeatedly refuses that role even though many, including Plato and Alcibiades, eagerly claim to be his students.

The Public’s production, then, shows us a Socrates who is as deeply compelling, frustrating and incomprehensible to his most Apollinian devotee (Plato) as he is to the most Dionysian (Alcibiades). This Socrates’ *atopia* extends to the fact that he cannot be securely placed with either Apollo or Dionysus. It can help us understand why, when Alcibiades searches for a way to capture the destabilizing, seductive and enigmatic power that Socrates exercises, especially on the *young*, he settles on a comparison to Marsyas, a Satyr who dares to compete in music with Apollo, except that he “needs no instruments to cast his spells” (65-6). In fact it is their mutual *draw* to Socrates that places the Apollinian Plato and the dionysian Alcibiades into the same orbit and even into conversation.

I have claimed that the reason to pay such careful attention to what is *not* in *Serenade*, as well as to what *is*, is that Ratmansky’s own work gives us good reason to suspect that even if the figure of Plato *has been* ballet’s most important philosophical interlocutor, the figure of *Socrates*

is equally if not more important for it going forward. For the time being, I have to allow this claim to remain, for the most part, a bald assertion. It is beyond the scope of this article to do justice to the many ways that Ratmansky's work, in my view, points in this direction. In conclusion, though, I want briefly to consider one reason to at least take an *interest* in that assertion.

Acocella, I have already argued, draws attention to the most significant way that *Serenade* does make contact with the specifics of the *Symposium* and, in particular, with the spirit of Socrates. For she shows the piece to depend upon a specific form of *love* between choreographer and dancer that is a form of just that love which lies at the heart of the *Symposium*. That form of love is also at the very heart of ballet as an art form. It is not something Ratmansky is introducing to it, but it is something his work re-introduces us to, helping us to remember that this is what ballet *is*, and to appreciate in new ways why it matters that ballet *is* that way.

One way that practitioners speak about this particular form of love is to speak of ballet as a "passing art."²² To call ballet *passing* art is in the first instance to call attention to the excruciating demands it makes on the individual: how short the time before such an art *passes out* of one's own particular body or being. It is also, though, to call attention to the way that such an art exists and persists only insofar as it is passed *from* one person *to* another, and only insofar as it is *received by* one person *from* another.²³

Diotima describes this process of *passing* by comparing it to the relation between an individual cell and a body: even as individual cells, which come to be and pass away, constitute a

²² I take this phrase from a lecture given by Edward Vilella on 6/11/18 at the International Ballet Competition, Jackson, MS.

²³ For a wonderful discussion of the central to philosophy, Socratically conceived, of this kind of passing from one individual persons to another, cf. Gréve 2018.

single body that both persists and changes over time, so a person gives life to something that will both persist and change as the individuals who give it life come to be and pass away. As Socrates understood it, *philosophy* was, and should remain, a passing art in this sense. What he and Plato quarrel most bitterly about in *The Public's* production is the question of whether it is a good idea for Plato to write the dialogues down. Plato argues that it is important to make the dialogues available in written form because for those who do not *know* Socrates it is better than nothing at all. Socrates, by contrast, worries that it will be worse; for someone with the illusion of philosophical conversation placed before them in this way will lose track of the basic *fact* that they are hungry and will be correspondingly less inclined to seek out whatever might in fact nourish them, whenever and wherever they can find it.

For the most part, this way of conceiving of what *philosophy is* has *passed out* of the profession. That profession is by and large comfortable with its modest place within the academy, comfortable conceiving itself as a theoretical discipline' rather than as a dialogic practice. But a version of the debate that Nelson dramatizes between Plato and Socrates remains very much alive within ballet. Perhaps to a degree that is true of no other western artform, ballet does not have something comparable to the option that Plato takes advantage of: no comparable way to create even the illusion that one has *the living thing itself* translated and preserved in written form on the page in front of one. Most plays have scripts and most people with even a passing interest in them can and do read them; compositions have scores, and even as a casual first-year piano student, I was learning the basics of how to read simple instances of those. But at the very top of his profession, Ratmansky himself could not read the notation in which Petipa's variations are recorded; he had to make a (quite controversial) decision to *learn* it.

The decision to embrace what limited notations ballet has at its disposal has remained firmly anchored in a deep commitment to ballet as a passing art. Although his decision to disappear into Harvard's archives has been much discussed, far less attention has been paid to his assiduous efforts to receive all he can from those still living who have experience of the ballets that he seeks to reconstruct. That commitment has also involved him, among other things, in traveling to a small gym in Jackson, Mississippi to teach the variations that he has just learned to the students at a relatively obscure ballet intensive and competitors who have been eliminated from an international competition, while engaging in heated discussion about the essence of a "glissade" with a few scattered international ballet luminaries from multiple generations, in front of an audience of young girls, ballet teachers and a random philosophy professor. If you had access to almost unlimited resources and carte blanche from companies around the world, is that what you would imagine choosing to do? Serious commitment to a passing art requires, as love always does, some seriously weird decisions.

Perhaps it would be seriously weird to decide that in order to go forward, ballet may need to push back, not just beyond contemporary productions of "classics" like *The Sleeping Beauty* and *La Bayadere* to the spirit, style and steps of the Petipa originals but also the reception of Plato as mediated either by Nietzsche or Neoplatonism to the spirit and style of the figure of Socrates who is disclosed in the Symposium itself. That, though, *is* my vision. If nothing else, it has helped me make my peace both with what is and what is *not* there in the extraordinary piece that is Ratmansky's *Serenade After Plato's Symposium*.

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Comparison of two versions of the Vision Scene in Act Two of The Sleeping Beauty (Ratmansky vs. Vikharev): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NxMfVNQQNk8>.